

Improving Congestion Control through Fine-Grain Monitoring of InfiniBand Networks

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Abstract—Congestion situations are a serious threat to the performance of the interconnection networks of High-Performance Computing and Data-Center systems. Hence, the specifications of the main interconnect technologies, such as InfiniBand, define some mechanisms to deal with congestion and its effects. However, these standard mechanisms may not be suitable to detect or track accurately the actual status of network congestion, as congestion dynamics indeed can be very complex and varied. Moreover, achieving an optimal configuration of the parameters that drive the different functionalities of congestion-control mechanisms is often a difficult task, as some configurations may be suitable for some traffic scenarios, but not for others. In this paper, we propose combining an existing light-weight platform monitoring tool (LIMITLESS) with the InfiniBand control software (OpenSM), such that the metrics about communication volumes in the network provided by the former allow the latter having a more precise image of congestion status, then being able to react more efficiently in these situations. The main contributions of this paper are the methodology to link the monitor and OpenSM, as well as modifications in the InfiniBand standard congestion-control mechanism so that its reaction is modulated based on the enhanced knowledge about congestion provided by the monitor. These improvements are ready to be integrated into any InfiniBand-based system. According to the results from our experiments (performed in a real InfiniBand-based cluster where we run a widely used benchmark), the proposed approach reduces significantly the number of wrong detections of congestion, and so the number of times that the congestion-control mechanisms react unnecessarily, hence improving system performance up to 74%. The overhead of this monitoring tool is 0.1% in our experiments, collecting data each 200ms.

Index Terms—Interconnection networks, cluster, congestion control, traffic monitoring, InfiniBand

I. INTRODUCTION

The interconnection network is a fundamental subsystem in High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters and Data-centers, where applications and services may generate billions of communication operations per second on thousands of computing or storage nodes. Consequently, high-speed and

low-latency interconnection networks are required to cope with those communication requirements, since otherwise the network may become the entire system bottleneck. One of the most successful high-performance interconnect technologies is the InfiniBand Architecture (IBA), widely deployed in many supercomputers, included the Top500 list [1]. Interconnection networks based on the IBA specification [2] are made of switches, host channel adapters (HCAs) and links, where switches contain a set of ports, and HCAs contain one (or several) ports to connect the computing or storage nodes to the network. These components allow building different topologies, such as Fat-Trees, Dragonflies or other low-diameter networks, extensively used in HPC systems.

Although there are proprietary control software for IBA-based hardware, there are some institutions that promote open-source drivers and control software for IBA-based networks such as the OpenSM [3]. One of the most important benefits of OpenSM is that network designers and administrators can modify the source code to improve the network operation, and to monitor the network performance. For instance, the OpenSM source code integrates the performance manager (*PerfMgr*) defined in the IBA specification, which instruments the performance metrics of IBA devices by means of the performance counters. They gather, at each device, information related to the traffic sent or the packets delay waiting to be injected in the network.

However, the performance of HPC systems is threatened when several applications generate network congestion, even if a properly configured IBA-based network is used. Congestion appears when several paths in the network are clogged due to traffic flows contending for them. These flows, hereafter referred to as *congesting flows*, can delay the forwarding of traffic flows not contributing to congestion, hereafter called *victim flows*. This effect is known as head-of-line (HoL) blocking, which significantly degrades the network performance. Hence, a mechanism to deal with congestion is required to reduce its impact on the network performance. Indeed, the IBA specification defines such a mechanism based on throttling the injection of congesting flows.

Unfortunately, congestion is by nature very dynamic, which means that a congestion tree may originate at some network point, later move to a different one, and so on. Hence, it is very complex to identify accurately and at any moment the flows

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contributing to a congestion root, and this leads to instabilities in the performance of networks using the IBA Congestion Control (CC) mechanism. Moreover, this mechanism needs a proper tuning of its configuration parameters to perform efficiently, which is very challenging, as many studies have reported [4], [5]. For this reason, we think that configuring and tuning dynamically the IBA CC parameters, based on the information provided by certain IBA performance counters, would improve the efficiency of the CC mechanism. This information can be gathered on-the-fly by means of a fine-grain monitoring system, then can send the collected information to the OpenSM to update the IBA CC parameters.

For that purpose, we propose combining the operation of OpenSM with an existing lightweight monitoring tool called LIMITLESS [6] [7], a monitor that can work under near-to-second sampling rates to provide the current IBA performance counters. Basically, the idea of our proposal is that LIMITLESS collects metrics about communication volumes in the network through the IBA performance counters at network devices. Then, LIMITLESS will provide OpenSM with a precise image of where congestion originates in the network and which is the degree of its severity. Finally, OpenSM configures the sources of congesting flows (end-nodes) to dynamically and precisely adjust their injections rates.

We have implemented our proposal in OpenSM and evaluated it in a real HPC cluster using an IBA-based network, specifically the cluster CELLIA, whose details can be found in Section IV-A. In more detail, we have extended the OpenSM source code to communicate with LIMITLESS and receive information about congestion, using the IBA performance counters at network devices. For the experimentation we use the Netgauge [8] and GPCNeT [9] benchmarks, activating either the traditional IBA CC or our proposal. Based on the results, we can conclude that our proposal outperforms the IBA CC when Netgauge and GPCNeT are running.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II overviews the InfiniBand Architecture and system monitoring. Section III describes our proposal to combine a monitoring system with congestion control proposed. Section IV describes the the experiments carried out in the real IBA-based cluster mentioned above and analyzes the obtained results. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Related InfiniBand Basics

In the following, we summarized the background details about the InfiniBand architecture and specification more closely related to the proposal described in Section III, such as addressing, buffering, congestion control, etc.

Routing in IBA-based networks is orchestrated by the subnet manager (SM), which discovers the network topology, assigns 16-bit addresses, denominated Local Identifiers (LIDs) to the network devices (i.e., HCAs and switches), and populates the routing tables at switches, based on the selected routing algorithm. Besides, each network device has a GUID (Global Unique Identifier), a 64-bit identifier assigned to each device

within a subnet. GUIDs are independent of LIDs. Although IBA-based networks support oblivious and adaptive routing, but in this work we focus on deterministic routing. The SM also reconfigures the network in runtime if eventual changes, faults or problems may happen. Once the SM finishes the setup stage, it becomes idle, but it may be run again if a network re-configuration is required. Current IBA-based networks widely use an implementation of the SM called OpenSM, included in the OpenFabrics Software (OFS) [10].

Regarding congestion control (CC), the IBA specification defines a CC mechanism based on throttling the injection of congesting flows. In more detail, the IBA CC enables two bits in the packet header for congestion notification: the FECN bit (*Forward Explicit Congestion Notification*) and the BECN bit (*Backward Explicit Congestion Notification*). The IBA CC follows a closed-loop approach based on the following steps. First, congestion points (roots) are detected inspecting the buffers occupancy at switches. When this occupancy exceeds a certain threshold, its associated output port enters the congestion state. Thereafter, packets crossing that port are considered as congesting, and they are marked, i.e., their FECN bit is enabled. When an HCA receives a FECN-marked packet, it sends back a notification packet with the BECN bit set, addressed to the source HCA of the FECN-marked packet. Source HCAs receiving BECNs will throttle the injection rate of those traffic flows addressed to the HCAs sending those BECNs. The injection throttling rate is defined at each HCA based on the BECNs reception rate, and on a set of parameters that are configured in advance by network administrators.

Specifically, when an HCA receives a BECN, the IBA CC mechanism applies an injection rate delay (IRD) to each traffic flow, prior to its injection in the network. The IRD is the delay between the injection of a packet and the injection of the next one of the same traffic flow. Each HCA holds a list of pre-configured IRDs stored in the congestion control table (CCT), that contains 128 entries. Thus, each HCA can apply 128 possible IRD values. The initial values of the CCT entries can be defined by the user in the OpenSM configuration.

HCAs internal memory is organized in a set of send/receive buffers, called queue pairs (QPs), each QP storing packets from traffic flows addressed to specific destinations, while waiting to be injected in the network. When a BECN is received at a given HCA, the corresponding QP injection rate is lowered according to the IRDs stored in the CCT. For each QP, the IBA CC defines a *CCTI_Index*, which points to an entry in the CCT, i.e., to a specific IRD value. Upon a BECN reception, the QP *CCTI_Index* is increased, pointing to another entry in the CCT with a higher value of the IRD. In this way the injection throttling rate for that flow is increased.

The IBA CC defines also the parameter *CCTI_Increase* to increase the value of the *CCTI_Index* every time a BECN is received. As the entries in the CCT table denote packet delays (these entries are sorted in ascending order), if the *CCTI_Index* is increased, this leads to an increase in the delays of subsequent packets. The typical value for *CCTI_Increase* is 1, and this value never changes during runtime. Therefore,

the *CCTI_Index* increases and decreases in a one-by-one basis, meaning that the IRD for a QP may be increased slowly. When congesting flows are throttled, the rate of BECNs reception at HCAs decreases as well. To decrease the IRD applied per QP, the IBA CC decreases the *CCTI_Index* every time a *Timer* expires and no BECNs have been received. When the *CCTI_Index* is 0, then no IRD is applied to the QP, meaning that congestion has disappeared. Unfortunately, the performance of IBA CC strongly depends of the tuning of the parameters described above, which is a real challenge [4].

Each network device stores utilization statistics in the performance counters, such as number of sent packets, number of received packets or time spent waiting to send a packet. There are multiple performance counters, but in this work we will focus on those used at server nodes to measure the congestion severity, specifically on *PortXmitWait*, that measures the number of hardware cycles spent by an HCA waiting to transmit packets due to insufficient credits in the next switch buffer, and on *PortXmitData*, that measures the number of bytes injected in the network from a given HCA.

B. System Monitoring

System monitoring for large-scale HPC platforms is a complex task, which becomes increasingly challenging as the scale and complexity of the infrastructure grows. A popular system monitor is Ganglia [11], which uses an all-to-all algorithm to receive information from the nodes. That policy increases monitor’s fault-tolerance at the expense of high communication and processing overheads, which increase the risk of network bottlenecks in large scale HPC systems. Another tool is Collectd [12], a daemon that collects system and application performance metrics. Its main strength is that it has a low overhead because it stores monitoring data at local nodes, needing further post-processing to gather and processing the information. This feature hampers the possibility of knowing global information in near real-time. Some other monitors, like Nagios [13] and DiMMon [14] are also used, but their main drawback is that they were not designed for HPC systems.

Most of the previous monitors are not adapted specifically to monitor InfiniBand networks. A generic work for monitoring tools for large scale systems showing examples for InfiniBand was presented in [15]. More recently, INAM [16] allows users to analyze and visualize the communication happening in the InfiniBand network (2000 nodes) to profile and visualize the communication with very low performance overhead at scale. Another work [17] proposed the inclusion of scripts to monitor the network. Finally, authors in [18] show an example of InfiniBand Network Analysis and Monitoring using (OpenSM).

LIMITLESS operates on each compute node and provides information about the platform resources and applications being executed. Compared to other HPC monitors, LIMITLESS has a low overhead, is scalable, and collects global information in logs that do not need further data recollection. In addition, LIMITLESS natively implements InfiniBand monitoring, so that this information can be exploited using OpenSM.

III. COMBINING CONGESTION CONTROL AND FINE-GRAIN MONITORING

This section describes our proposal to use the LIMITLESS’s fine-grain monitoring tool to gather the performance counters at the devices of an IBA-based network, leveraging this information to dynamically tune some of the IBA CC parameters, and improve the network performance. First, we describe the system monitor architecture and how the performance counters are collected; next, we detail how the CC parameters are reconfigured based on the collected information; finally, we provide the implementation details in OpenSM.

A. Monitoring architecture

In this work LIMITLESS is used to constantly monitor the cluster, and to collect and relay information about the current state of the network to the IBA OpenSM. The monitoring system consists of three different components that cooperate to transport the performance information from the nodes and HCAs to OpenSM. The architecture is based on a Tree-Based Overlay Network (TBON), and it offers simplicity, scalability, and fault tolerance. The final stage of this process consists in storing the metrics in a database to visualize the data. However, in this work, the integration has been done directly with the IBA OpenSM, to minimize the time to collect information and reconfigure the network.

The main components of the monitoring system are: *Daemon Monitor* (LDM), *Daemon Aggregator* (LDA) and *Daemon Server* (LDS). More precisely, the LDM process periodically collects the information about the IBA performance counters (i.e., *PortXmitWait*), and sends it to the OpenSM process to reconfigure the IBA CC parameters. The LDM is executed in every server node and queries the performance counters of the node’s IBA HCA. LDA transforms the data *in-transit* received from LDMs (in order to reduce the network traffic) and re-transmits the information to the next monitoring component. The LDS is the component in charge of receiving, processing, and storing the metrics collected from the HCAs.

With this monitoring tool it is possible to collect the monitoring metrics and re-configure the CC parameters of the whole cluster every 200ms. The overhead produced by the monitor has been measured by collecting the time that the monitor has been in execution and the average load that is reached. For each hour of execution, the monitor consumes 3.98 seconds with an average load 0.1% of CPU. Note the small monitoring overhead.

B. Dynamic reconfiguration of the IBA CC Parameters

The main idea behind our proposal is to dynamically modify the configuration of the IBA CC parameters at those HCAs that generate traffic flows and contribute to congestion, based on the information provided by the monitor. In these HCAs, we apply a more aggressive injection rate delay (IRD) to congesting flows, which permits to efficiently react to the network congestion and prevent its negative effects. To detect whether an HCA is contributing to congestion, we look at the *PortXmitWait* value provided by LIMITLESS to OpenSM for

each HCA. This value refers to the number of processor clock cycles that a specific HCA has to wait in order to inject traffic into the network. If this value exceeds the *upper_limit* value, then the HCA is waiting too much, which is an early indicator to identify that this HCA might be contributing to congestion.

When a given HCA with a high *PortXmitWait* value is truly contributing to congestion, packets generated by this HCA will be marked, and sooner or later BECN notifications will be received. As the OpenSM also updates the *CCTI_Increase* for that HCA, the injection throttling is applied in that HCA. However, high values for *PortXmitWait* can be observed in HCAs generating victim flows, which we do not want to throttle. Note that these HCAs will not receive BECN notifications, so that the injection throttling will not be enabled, which is an advantage for our proposal. When the *PortXmitWait* value drops below a *lower_limit*, this is an indication that the IBA-CC is reacting and/or congestion is vanishing. In this moment, we set the *CCTI_Increase* parameter to zero, so that the injection throttling is disabled in that HCA. Algorithm 1 shows the reconfiguration algorithm described above.

OpenSM configures the CC mechanism using the recommended values for the parameters [4], but with the *CCTI_Increase* parameter equal to zero, so HCAs discard the received BECNz and no injection throttling is applied. Indeed, the CC is not enabled at HCAs until LIMITLESS reports the OpenSM that the *PortXmitWait* exceeds the *upper_limit*. Hence, OpenSM needs to check the *PortXmitWait* value for all the HCAs in the network, at the same rate as these values are provided by LIMITLESS. Note that any new configuration for the *CCTI_Increase* parameter of a given HCA (either to enable or disable that parameter) is sent by the OpenSM to that HCA, via management datagrams (MADs). Moreover, OpenSM knows if the HCA has already been updated, so it is possible to avoid to continuously send MADs with the *CCTI_Increase* parameter configuration to the HCAs.

C. OpenSM implementation

This section describes the changes made in OpenSM (v3.3.19 for this proposal) to include the proposal defined in the previous section. As we describe later in Section IV-A, we have evaluated our proposal in a real cluster using an IBA-based network, where we have built a slimmed fat-tree and a KNS topology. As far as we know, this is the first time that the later topology is implemented with IBA hardware, hence we have had to include in OpenSM a new routing engine, called *hdor*, that implements the Hybrid-DOR routing algorithm [19] defined for KNS topologies. We have also implemented our proposal in the *ftree* routing engine available in OpenSM.

The *hdor* and *ftree* routing engines (hereafter REs) use several functions provided by the OpenSM congestion control manager (*CCMgr*) to exchange MADs with the IBA devices. These functions are *osm_RE_send_ca_cong_setting* and *osm_RE_mad_post*. The first one is used to encapsulate in a MAD the current tuning of the congestion control

parameters. The second one is used to send the MAD to its corresponding HCA.

The monitor provides OpenSM with the performance counters information in a temporary file, updated periodically (approximately every 200 ms). This file has one line per node in the network. Each line contains the GUID, and the value of the IBA performance counters of the corresponding HCA. OpenSM needs to read and process this file faster than LIMITLESS collects the corresponding information. To read this information, the OpenSM REs include a function called *RE_read_monitor*, which is run periodically. The *RE_read_monitor* function obtains the *PortXmitWait* value for all the HCAs in the network, and supply this information to another function, called *RE_cc_update_hca* that implements Algorithm 1. This function decides if the CC parameters at a given HCA need to be updated.

Fig. 1: A 36-node 3-stage slimmed fat-tree (SFT). Green nodes are used in the GPCNeT benchmark to measure performance, while orange nodes are used to generate congestion.

Fig. 2: A 36-node 6-ary 2-direct 1-indirect (KNS). Green nodes are used in the GPCNeT benchmark to measure performance, while orange nodes are used to generate congestion.

IV. EVALUATION RESULTS

A. Hardware testbed configuration

CELLIA (Cluster for the Evaluation of Low-Latency Interconnection Architectures) consists of 50 server nodes HP Proliant DL120 Gen9, with a processor Intel Xeon E5-2630v3 8-cores at 1.80 GHz and 16 GB of RAM. The interconnec-

Algorithm 1 *CC_Update_HCAs*: It decides whether to update the CC parameters in the HCAs.

Input Parameters: upper_limit, lower_limit, ccti_new_value

```

1: for all HCAs in the Subnet do
2:   if (!cc_modified and
      port_xmit_wait > upper_limit) then
3:     cc_modified ← true
4:     ccti_increase ← ccti_new_value
5:     send_new_cc_conf_to_hca()
6:   end if
7:   if (cc_modified and
      port_xmit_wait < lower_limit) then
8:     cc_modified ← false
9:     ccti_increase ← 0
10:    send_default_cc_conf_to_hca()
11:  end if
12: end for

```

tion network is built with IBA-based hardware¹. Specifically, CELLIA has 50 Mellanox IS5022 8-port switches with QDR technology, each link offering 40 Gbps. We use QSFP copper cables with 4x QDR links. Each server node has a dual-port Mellanox ConnectX3 MCX353A-QCBT HCA with 40Gpbs.

We have configured two different network topologies in CELLIA, in both cases connecting 36 server nodes: a 3-stage slimmed fat-tree (SFT) [20] (see Figure 1) and a KNS topology [19] (see Figure 2). The SFT has been chosen as a very well known reference topology, due to its popularity and widespread use in HPC systems; on the other hand, the KNS topology has been chosen as an interesting novel, hybrid alternative to traditional networks (so novel that it required a new OpenSM routing engine, as explained in Section III-C).

Note that, while SFTs can be easily built with IBA-based hardware, KNS topologies require that IBA network interfaces re-route packets between their ports without the intervention of the node hardware, similarly to the network interfaces in direct networks. As this functionality is not available in the CELLIA hardware, we have used switches acting as routers, each “router” having a single node connected via its HCA. As far as we know the rerouting support is not yet available in commercial hardware. However, recent InfiniBand-based HCAs, such as ConnectX-6, offer virtual switching offload capabilities in the hardware (i.e Enhanced vSwitch) “for future protocols” (e.g. Hybrid-DOR). Therefore, when the re-routing support is ready at the network interfaces (which is doable with the current technology), KNS networks could be built without need of additional switches acting as routers.

For the experiments carried out in this paper, we have used three configurations regarding congestion control: no congestion control, standard (i.e., “static”) IBA congestion control,

¹Note that CELLIA does not count with the most up-to-date interconnect components, but the ones available in the cluster are enough to check the viability and efficiency of our proposal. Moreover, the described implementation is perfectly valid for more modern hardware.

and our proposal to dynamically tune the CC parameters based on the monitor information. The most relevant parameters of the IBA-CC mechanism can be found in Table I.

TABLE I: Congestion control and monitor configuration.

	Parameter	Value
Common parameters	<i>Threshold</i>	0x7
	<i>Packet_Size</i>	1
	<i>Marking_Rate</i>	0x000f
	<i>CCTI_Timer</i>	150
	<i>CCTI_Increase</i>	{1,2,5,10,20}
Our proposal’s parameters	<i>Upper_limit (see Algorithm 1)</i>	0.850 ms
	<i>Lower_limit (see Algorithm 1)</i>	0.055 ms

Note that we have used different values for *CCTI_Increase* to study the impact of the variations of this parameter on the CC efficiency. The rest of parameters have been configured as recommended in other studies [4].

B. Network workloads

The CELLIA cluster includes Netgauge [8] and GPCNeT [9], two benchmarks that are commonly used in HPC systems to measure the network performance. Netgauge is a high-precision network parameter measurement tool, which supports many different network protocols and communication patterns, like efficient bisection bandwidth (*ebb*) or many-to-one (*Nto1*). Specifically, the *ebb* communication pattern measures the effective bisection bandwidth, as defined in [21], by generating several random traffic patterns and computing the bisection bandwidth on those patterns. For the *Nto1* traffic pattern, N-1 processes (where $N = 36$ in our cluster) communicate data to a chosen single destination (hot-spot), and it sends data back to them. We have executed Netgauge with 36 MPI tasks (i.e., one MPI task per end node in the cluster) both for the Fat-tree and KNS topologies.

GPCNeT is generally used to measure the impact of congestion in HPC systems. It has been tested in systems such as Cray or Summit. GPCNeT randomly chooses 20% of the nodes (i.e., the probe nodes) to calculate the performance metrics and the rest of the nodes to generate congesting traffic (i.e., the congestor nodes). We have tweaked GPCNeT so that the probe nodes chosen randomly are the same in the SFT and the KNS topology. Figures 1 and 2 show the probe nodes (in green) and the congestor nodes (in orange). We have run GPCNeT using 8 MPI ranks per node both for both topologies. GPCNeT offers performance metrics by means of several tests:

- *Random Ring Point-to-point Latency (P2P Lat)*. The MPI tasks of the probe nodes are sorted in a Random Ring structure, each task sending 8-Byte messages to a neighbor in the ring and receiving 8-Byte messages from the other neighbor in the ring. Note that in this test, the latency of the packets is measured in microseconds (μs).
- *Random Ring Point-to-point Bandwidth with Synchronization (P2PBW+Sync)*. In the same structure mentioned above, eight 128 KB messages are sent to and received from the left and right neighbours (16 messages in total), which are typically enough messages to achieve

Fig. 3: Network Throughput for the Netgauge *Nto1* communication pattern (MBit/s) versus packet size (Bytes) in logarithmic scale. *CCTI_Increase* is set to 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20.

peak bandwidth [9]. This test is sensitive to bandwidth contention and latency from the synchronization.

- *AllReduce*. Small (8-Byte) MPI *AllReduce* operations are executed. This test is used to measure the congestion impact on latency-sensitive collective communication.

For each test, GPCNeT first runs the tests mentioned above without congestion, so that the congestor nodes do not generate traffic. Next the congestor nodes stress the network, running again the previous tests. Moreover, in our experiments with Netgauge and GPCNeT, we have also analyzed the values provided by LIMITLESS for the IBA network performance counters, such as *portXmitData* and *portXmitWait*.

C. Netgauge results analysis

Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6 show the experimental results for the *Nto1* and *ebb* tests of Netgauge using three configurations: no congestion control (“WithoutCC”), typical InfiniBand CC (“CC”) and our proposal (called “LIMITLESS+CC” in the plots). Note that for CC and LIMITLESS+CC several series of results are shown in figures 4 and 6, corresponding to different values of *CCTI_Increase*. Figure 3 shows no performance gain for “LIMITLESS+CC” compared to “CC” and “WithoutCC” configurations, since the *Nto1* traffic pattern does not generate victim flows (i.e., all the traffic flows are congesting).

However, if we observe the *PortXmitData* and *PortXmitWait* performance counters, we can see interesting results. Figure 4 shows the performance counters values versus time during the execution time of the *Nto1* test (around 22 seconds). We have set the *CCTI_Increase* parameter to 5, which is an intermediate value making the injection throttling more sensitive to network traffic status. *PortXmitData* measures the injection rate in node 30 (similar results can be observed in other nodes), which is similar for the three CC configurations, as the *Nto1* traffic pattern does not generate victim flows. The *PortXmitWait* results, measured in ms, show that, when we use “LIMITLESS+CC”, the packets are waiting to be injected for a significantly shorter period of time. As the *CCTI_Increase* parameter has a higher value than that of the CC mechanism, then for “LIMITLESS+CC” the network bandwidth is fairly shared among the *N* nodes generating traffic. Therefore, the injection throttling is working smoothly with our proposal, regardless the network topology (i.e., SFT of KNS).

Figures 5 and 6 show the experimental results for the Netgauge *ebb* communication pattern. Note that *ebb* generates traffic flows small in size, and their destination is chosen randomly following a uniform distribution. Hence, the *ebb* test does not generate long-lived congestion situations.

As we can see in Figure 5, there is a significant per-

(a) *PortXmitData* in SFT.

(b) *PortXmitWait* in SFT.

(c) *PortXmitData* in KNS.

(d) *PortXmitWait* in KNS.

Fig. 4: Results for the *PortXmitData* and *PortXmitWait* performance counters in node 30 with the *NtoI* communication pattern versus Time ($CCTI_Increase = 5$).

formance degradation when CC is configured with higher $CCTI_Increase$ values, and these differences are even worse in the KNS topology. However, these differences are minimized when LIMITLESS+CC is used. It reduces the effort to tune the $CCTI_Increase$ value.

Figure 6 shows the results for the *PortXmitData* and *PortXmitWait* in node 30 when using the *ebb* communication pattern. *PortXmitData* results show a typical case of injection rate oscillations in the nodes.

Note that the best choice would be to not enable the throttling under light congestion, but if this is not a choice for the network administrator, then we would recommend enabling our proposal since it handles better the light congestion, compared to the traditional CC mechanism. If we observe the *PortXmitWait* results for CC, packets do not need to wait too much in average to be injected. When light congestion arises, CC triggers immediately the throttling of the traffic flows generating light congestion even though this congestion is not dangerous. For this reason, the CC mechanism shows the worst results for *PortXmitData*. Note that the *PortXmitWait* values for “LIMITLESS+CC” and “WithoutCC” remain well below 0.85ms, which is exactly the value of the *upper_limit* parameter (see Table I), so that the injection throttling is not enabled unless *PortXmitWait* values are higher than 0.85ms.

D. GPCNeT results analysis

Table II shows the results for the GPCNeT P2PBW+Sync test. We have focused on this GPCNeT test since we are interested in the bandwidth results. Note that the CELLIA cluster facility is small compared to largest supercomputers in the world, or those facilities where GPCNeT has been used in the past. Note that the experiments in this work are a proof-of-concept to demonstrate that our proposal is able to leverage the monitoring information, and to avoid the traditional IBA CC mechanism overreaction when congestion is light or inaccuracy when congestion is strong.

We have colored in green the table cells where LIMITLESS+CC outperforms CC. As can be seen, our proposal outperforms most of the times CC no matter if there is light congestion (“Without Cong.” rows in the table) or strong congestion (“With Cong.” rows in the table), and regardless the network topology (i.e., SFT or KNS). Note also that our proposal remains invariant to the different $CCTI_Increase$ values, meaning that this approach would save effort to the network administrators, as they would not need to pay attention to configure the $CCTI_Increase$ parameter. As we have mentioned above, even though CELLIA is a small facility, we still can see how our proposal outperforms CC and achieves

(a) ebb CC in SFT.

(b) ebb LIMITLESS+CC in SFT.

(c) ebb CC in KNS.

(d) ebb LIMITLESS+CC in KNS.

Fig. 5: Network Throughput for the Netgauge *ebb* communication pattern (MBit/s) versus packet size (Bytes) in logarithmic scale. *CCTI_Increase* parameter is set to 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20.

TABLE II: Average (Avg) and 99-th tile (99th) GPCNet P2PBW+Sync results (MiB/s/rank) for the KNS and SFT topologies, using IBA CC and LIMITLESS+CC (LIM+CC).

		CCTI Increase Values					
		1	2	5	10	20	
SFT	With Cong.	Avg	CC 76,20	82,60	77,50	85,70	82,30
		LIM+CC	80,50	75,60	79,20	76,20	78,90
		Speedup	0.06	-0.08	0.02	-0.11	-0.04
	99th	CC	63,20	63,90	62,20	68,10	62,90
		LIM+CC	65,80	62,70	64,60	59,60	63,20
		Speedup	-0.04	0.02	-0.04	0.14	0.00
Without Cong.	Avg	CC	200,20	146,60	183,40	137,30	159,30
		LIM+CC	170,40	177,20	181,30	173,00	170,00
		Speedup	-0.15	0.21	-0.01	0.26	0.07
	99th	CC	167,40	122,20	153,90	118,90	130,50
		LIM+CC	131,10	142,00	123,90	137,30	133,10
		Speedup	-0.22	0.16	-0.19	0.15	0.02
KNS	With Cong.	Avg	CC 175,10	111,10	130,80	110,90	111,10
		LIM+CC	125,90	175,60	137,70	140,40	142,00
		Speedup	-0.28	0.58	0.05	0.27	0.28
	99th	CC	115,70	107,20	107,70	107,20	107,40
		LIM+CC	107,10	115,00	106,90	107,00	107,10
		Speedup	-0.07	0.07	-0.01	0.00	0.00
Without Cong.	Avg	CC	288,40	200,20	268,00	178,90	226,60
		LIM+CC	288,20	284,30	288,00	285,40	286,30
		Speedup	0.00	0.42	0.07	0.60	0.26
	99th	CC	253,60	155,70	213,10	148,10	176,00
		LIM+CC	273,10	270,40	269,70	268,90	269,30
		Speedup	0.08	0.74	0.27	0.82	0.53

a more accurate reaction to congestion scenarios.

Figure 7 shows the results for the *PortXmitData* (in GB/s) and *PortXmitWait* (in milliseconds waited in average to send

data) performance counters values, obtained when running the complete GPCNeT benchmark. During the execution of GPCNeT, first the P2P Lat test is run, then the P2PBW+Sync and finally the AllReduce test. These tests last around 40 seconds, and they only generate traffic in the probe nodes (i.e., those colored in green in Figures 1 and 2). After this period of time, the congestor nodes (i.e., the ones colored in orange in Figures 1 and 2) generate strong congestion. In the case of the SFT topology, the *PortXmitData* results show that, when there is no congestion, “LIMITLESS+CC” configuration obtains the best results, outperforming the “WithoutCC” configuration. Note that the *PortXmitWait* values range from 0 to 0.5 ms in this scenario. Note also that the performance obtained by GPCNeT in the KNS topology is significantly higher than that in the SFT, since the former has a higher bisection bandwidth.

Furthermore, when congestion starts after 40 seconds, the amount of traffic delivered by the network is reduced to 250 MB/s for the SFT and to 1 GB/s for the KNS topology (see the *PortXmitData* values). Note that congestor nodes (80% as defined by GPCNet) generate a big amount of traffic, so that congestion impacts on the overall network performance. Although the “LIMITLESS+CC” bandwidth results for the SFT topology are similar to those of “CC”, note that for the KNS

Fig. 6: *PortXmitData* (MB/s) and *PortXmitWait* (ms) values in node 30 with the *ebb* communication pattern versus Time (*CCTI_Increase* = 5).

topology “LIMITLESS+CC” outperforms “CC”, which does not react properly to congestion. On the other hand, the values for the *PortXmitWait* indicate that the time waited to send data for the “LIMITLESS+CC” and “WithoutCC” configurations significantly increases (up to 3ms) when congestion appears, but there is also more traffic injected in the network compared to the “CC” mechanism, since the latter mechanism always reacts behind the schedule to congestion, allowing the injection of traffic from congesting sources when it should throttle them.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented a new proposal to leverage a fine-grain monitoring tool (LIMITLESS) to obtain accurate information of congestion situations, appearing in InfiniBand (IBA) networks. We have extended the OpenSM control software of IBA networks to use the LIMITLESS obtained information, and configure the IBA congestion control (CC) to operate with a higher accuracy. The main drawback of the traditional IBA CC mechanism is that network administrators need to tune a set of configuration parameters depending on the expected traffic conditions, network topology and routing algorithms. This tuning can be time consuming and not always assures the CC mechanism to operate successfully, especially if traffic conditions may vary. As a solution, our proposal

enables OpenSM to dynamically configure the IBA CC parameters during runtime, so that server nodes do not overreact throttling the traffic flows unnecessarily. We have evaluated our proposal in a real cluster by running real applications, such as the Netgauge and GPCNeT benchmarks, widely used to measure the congestion impact in high-speed interconnects. From the performed experiments, we observe that our proposal reduces the overreaction of the CC mechanism regardless the congestion severity, while easing the configuration of the corresponding parameters. As future work, we will extend our implementation in OpenSM with distributed processing of collected information, leveraging the Subnet Agents to share performance counters.

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Fig. 7: GPCNeT Results versus Time for the *PortXmitData* and *PortXmitData* performance counters. Congestion starts after 40 seconds ($CCTI_Increase = 5$).

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